

Tactical Demand and Capacity Balancing with Uncertainty Using Incremental Path-Search based on Spatio-Temporal Graph

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Abstract—Demand and Capacity Balancing (DCB) operations, typically implemented pre-flight, face limitations in effectiveness due to uncertainties during air traffic operations. Therefore, executing DCB during the tactical phase (as close to the departure time as possible) holds promise for better addressing these uncertainties. This study proposes a tactical-phase DCB method that accounts for uncertainties to meet practical application scenarios and requirements, e.g., considering dynamic environment and fairness. The large-scale (e.g., national or continental) tactical DCB problem is transformed into a hotspot-free trajectory planning problem based on sequential planning to accommodate the diverse performance preferences of stakeholders, i.e., air navigation service providers and airlines. An adaptive directed spatio-temporal graph method is introduced, enabling the integration optimisation of multiple air traffic flow management measures (ground delay, rerouting, and speed control) while considering flight uncertainties and fuel consumption constraints. An incremental path search method is also developed to significantly accelerate problem-solving and meet tactical operational demands, ensuring optimal solutions by designing an admissible heuristic function. Simulation experiments based on historical European air traffic data demonstrate that the proposed method can resolve all overloaded (demand over capacity) air traffic service units. Compared to the computer-assisted slot allocation method currently used in European operations, the proposed approach reduces the number of delayed flights and average delay time by approximately 79.4% and 92.1%, respectively.

Keywords—air traffic management, demand and capacity balancing, air traffic flow management, trajectory planning, uncertainty, spatio-temporal graph, incremental search

I. INTRODUCTION

Demand and Capacity Balancing (DCB) is a cornerstone of efficient and safe Air Traffic Management (ATM), addressing the challenges of growing air traffic demand and limited airspace capacity [1] [2]. Effective DCB ensures operational safety and minimises delays, fuel consumption, and environmental impacts [3] [4]. However, the implementation of DCB is hindered by significant uncertainties in airspace operations, such as unpredictable weather conditions, fluctuating demand patterns, and trajectory deviations [5]. These uncertainties often lead to suboptimal decisions that exacerbate delays, increase operational costs, and reduce overall system efficiency. Consequently, addressing uncertainties in DCB operations remains a critical priority for enhancing the robustness of Air Traffic Flow Management (ATFM) systems [6].

Some recent studies aim to mitigate operational uncertainty by improving prediction accuracy. For instance, machine learning models for trajectory prediction have been shown to enhance the accuracy of DCB decisions [7]. However, this prediction-based approach has significant limitations: the air traffic system is a highly complex system influenced by numerous dynamic factors such as weather, demand fluctuations, and unexpected events, making precise predictions inherently challenging. In this context, tactical DCB is increasingly recognised as an effective strategy for managing operational uncertainty [8]. As tactical DCB is implemented closer to flight departure times, it benefits from reduced uncertainty and can leverage real-time or near-real-time data to make more reliable decisions under dynamically changing traffic patterns and airspace conditions [9].

However, solving DCB problems during the tactical phase remains a formidable challenge due to their large-scale nature and the need for rapid computation [10]. DCB optimisation often involves balancing conflicting objectives, such as minimising delays, fuel consumption, and air traffic controller workload, within a constrained timeframe [11]. Most existing DCB methods rely on single-strategy approaches, such as ground delay, to manage capacity-demand imbalances [12] [13]. While straightforward, these methods often fail to fully exploit the available airspace capacity and may lead to suboptimal performance under complex and congested scenarios. Incorporating multiple ATFM measures, such as rerouting, speed control, and ground delay, within a unified optimisation framework can offer a more comprehensive solution [14]. Yet, this integration increases computational complexity, posing significant challenges for real-time tactical operations [15].

Another pressing issue is the limited transparency and fairness of DCB methods, which hinder their practical adoption and acceptance among stakeholders [16]. For instance, black-box optimisation models, which lack explainability, may lead to distrust among airspace users, including airlines and air navigation service providers [17]. Furthermore, ensuring fairness in DCB solutions, such as equitable distribution of delays across flights, remains a critical concern for maintaining stakeholder cooperation [18]. Without addressing these issues, the practical integration of advanced DCB methods into operational systems is unlikely to achieve widespread acceptance.

This paper proposes a tactical DCB method with practical application potential, designed to efficiently respond to operational uncertainties. The contributions of this work are summarised as follows:

- 1) The large-scale tactical DCB problem is transformed into a hotspot-free trajectory planning problem based on sequential planning, which is more conducive to building a relatively fair and transparent solution mechanism and adapting to the differentiated performance preferences of stakeholders.
- 2) An adaptive directed spatio-temporal graph method is proposed, achieving integration optimisation using three ATFM measures (i.e., ground delay, rerouting, and speed control) simultaneously, while also accommodating flight uncertainty and fuel consumption constraints.
- 3) An incremental path search method is introduced to significantly accelerate the solution process, thus meeting tactical operational demands, and by designing an admissible heuristic function, the optimal solution is ensured.

The rest of the paper is structured as follows: [section II](#) defines the DCB problem, [section III](#) details the proposed method, [section IV](#) presents the experiments and results, and [section V](#) summarises the findings.

II. PROBLEM DESCRIPTION

This study was performed as a part of a SESAR exploratory research project, **HYPERSOLVER**: Artificial Intelligence controller able to manage Air traffic Control (ATC) and ATFM within a single framework. In the HYPERSOLVER framework ([Figure 1](#)), ATFM and ATC are designed as a holistic closed-loop system, serving as inputs and feedback to each other. ATFM is used for density management, and due to the need to respond dynamically to changes in the tactical phase of ATC, its implementation time is set to one hour before departure ([Figure 2](#)). AI component includes a DCB solver and a CDR solver, which are used for human-AI teaming with the Network management officer from the Network Manager (NM) and air traffic controller from the Air Navigation Service Provider (ANSP) through Human-Machine Interfaces to support the holistic ATFM-ATC system operation. This research focuses on developing the DCB solver to meet HYPERSOLVER’s design requirements:

- **Dynamic Environment:** The solver needs to consider uncertainties to some extent in order to cope with changes in the tactical operating environment.
- **High-Speed Computation:** It should be capable of performing rapid calculations close to the time of departure to enable continuous and fast loop iterations with ATC.
- **Fairness and Transparency:** The algorithmic strategies should be fair and transparent to gain acceptance from the community.
- **High customisability:** It should allow for a high degree of customisation in optimisation objectives, constraints, and DCB strategy selection (e.g., ground delay, speed control, rerouting, and their combination), to ensure com-

patibility with the operational performance preferences and constraints of Airspace Users (AUs).

Figure 1. HYPERSOLVER framework: holistic ATFM-ATC system based on human-AI teaming. This paper focuses on the DCB solver.

Figure 2. DCB solving based on sliding block. According to the relevant regulations of ICAO and EUROCONTROL [19] [20], this paper assumes that flight plans are submitted at least 3 hours prior to departure. At a specific moment (typically on the hour, such as 8 am), the previous hour (e.g., 7–8 am) is referred to as the solving slot, where the DCB solver is used to solve flights departing within the subsequent 2 hours (e.g., 8–10 am), which are defined as a regulated block. The same method is applied sequentially to solve each regulated block. Note that the duration of the solving slot and regulated block can be adjusted based on actual requirements.

In this study, the DCB problem is formulated as follows: before departure, flight plans are regulated through ground delay, speed control, rerouting, or their combinations to ensure that no overloads occur (i.e., demand exceeding capacity within a time window) while minimising additional operational costs such as fuel consumption and delays. To clarify further, the DCB problems are explained as follows:

- Assumptions
 - Flight uncertainty is taken into account; however, as a preliminary study, the uncertainty is broadly abstracted using a commonly used distribution model, without yet incorporating the true underlying uncertainty distributions.
 - The change in aircraft motion state is instantaneous.
 - Only cruise trajectories are focused, and changes in flight altitude are not considered.
 - Demand counting uses the entry count [12], i.e., a flight is counted as a demand for an Air Traffic Service Unit (ATSU) within a time window when it exactly enters the ATSU.
 - Regardless of whether the flight departs within the area where the DCB is implemented, its flight plan can be regulated.
 - Each flight has a preset maximum fuel consumption within the airspace of interest.
- Constraints

III. METHODOLOGY

To meet the development requirements of the DCB solver described, this study explores the following technical approach:

- 1) The large-scale DCB problem in the tactical phase is transformed into a hotspot-free trajectory planning problem (where hotspot refers to overloaded ATSU) based on sequential planning, i.e., First-come, First-Served (FCFS). By solving for each flight independently, this approach reduces the complexity of the problem while enabling optimisation tailored to individual performance preferences and specific constraints.
- 2) The computationally intensive hotspot detection formulas, which account for flight uncertainty, are reformulated into iterative expressions. This significantly improves the speed of hotspot identification (subsection III-A).
- 3) A spatio-temporal graph model is constructed for hotspot-free trajectory planning to achieve a high degree of customisation. For each flight, this model allows a flexible selection of different ATFM measures (e.g., ground holding, speed control, and rerouting) and adjustable model parameters (e.g., fuel consumption limits, and allowable speed ranges) (subsection III-B).
- 4) A constrained incremental pathfinding algorithm is developed to meet the computational speed requirements of the tactical phase. This enables trajectory searches without the need to generate a complete spatio-temporal graph, greatly saving time. Additionally, an admissible heuristic function is designed for the algorithm to ensure the generation of optimal trajectories (subsection III-C).

A. DCB fast discriminant based on probability

In this study, a trajectory is represented as a series of consecutive waypoints and their corresponding CTAs. These waypoints are the entry/exit points of adjacent ATSUs. For example, as shown in Figure 4, flight i 's trajectory F_i can be represented as:

$$F_i = \{(p_{i,1}, t_{i,1}), (p_{i,2}, t_{i,2}), (p_{i,3}, t_{i,3}), \dots\} \quad (1)$$

where $p_{i,n}$ denotes the position of flight i 's n -th waypoint and $t_{i,n}$ is its corresponding CTA. Considering that the flight can

- DCB constraint: In any time window of any ATSU, demand must always be less than or equal to capacity.
- Speed constraint: The flight speed must be within the performance range of the aircraft.
- Fuel consumption constraint: The fuel consumption within the airspace of interest must not exceed the preset value.

- Objectives

- Minimise delay time.
- Minimise fuel consumption.

The workflow of the tactical DCB solver in this study is illustrated in Figure 3. The workflow primarily involves three main stakeholders: NM, AUs, and ANSPs. Their interactions in the workflow are as follows:

- **AUs** submit the flight plans to NM before the departure of flights (including aircraft details, departure/arrival times, and waypoints with corresponding CTAs), as well as performance preferences (e.g., delay minimisation), and flight constraints (e.g., upper fuel consumption limit).
- **ANSPs** continuously update NM with the current airspace state (e.g., real-time flight operation data and weather forecasts) and airspace operation limits (e.g., speed restrictions).
- **NM** is responsible for managing and executing the tactical DCB solver. Specifically:
 - Potential demand is derived from the flight plans submitted by AUs.
 - Remaining capacity is predicted based on the current airspace state provided by ANSPs.
 - The performance preferences submitted by AUs define the optimisation objectives, while the flight constraints from AUs and the airspace operation limits from ANSPs serve as constraints in the optimisation problem.
 - The solver generates regulated flight plans as solutions, which are then updated and communicated to the relevant AUs and ANSPs.

Figure 3. Workflow of tactical DCB operation, where tactical DCB solver runs once in each solving slot, starting with AUs and ANSPs share information with NM and ending with NM update regulated flight plans to corresponding AUs and ANSPs.

Figure 4. Flight plan, consisting of waypoints on the ATSU boundaries in flight order and their corresponding CTAs.

detect and correct the deviation from the CTA upon reaching each waypoint, we simplify the problem by assuming that the uncertainty of arrival time of the flight at waypoint $\mathbf{p}_{i,n}$ follows a probability distribution $f(t)$ with a mean of $t_{i,n}$ and a standard deviation of $\sigma(t_{i,n}, \overrightarrow{\mathbf{p}_{i,n-1}\mathbf{p}_{i,n}})$. Among the distribution model, $\sigma(t_{i,n}, \overrightarrow{\mathbf{p}_{i,n-1}\mathbf{p}_{i,n}})$ denotes a function of $t_{i,n}, \overrightarrow{\mathbf{p}_{i,n-1}\mathbf{p}_{i,n}}$, where $t_{i,n}, \overrightarrow{\mathbf{p}_{i,n-1}\mathbf{p}_{i,n}}$ denotes the flight time from $\mathbf{p}_{i,n-1}$ to $\mathbf{p}_{i,n}$ with the speed $v_{i,n}, \overrightarrow{\mathbf{p}_{i,n-1}\mathbf{p}_{i,n}}$ corresponding flight i on this segment. It should be noted that the method introduced in this paper is compatible with any probabilistic distribution model that can be mathematically formulated. In the DCB problem, a day is typically divided into several time windows, such as 72, with each time window lasting 20 minutes. Based on the arrival time uncertainty distribution model, we use $p_{i,j,k}$ to represent the probability of flight i entering ATSU j during time window k , which can be expressed as:

$$p_{i,j,k} = \int_{k\Delta T}^{(k+1)\Delta T} f(t) dt \quad (2)$$

Although air traffic operation is a complex system, in order to simplify this DCB problem, when calculating occupancy probability, the occupancy of time window k of ATSU j by different flights is assumed as independent events. Therefore, the probability $p_{j,k}^{\text{NH}}$ that time window k of ATSU j is not a hotspot is expressed as:

$$p_{j,k}^{\text{NH}} = \sum_{q=0}^{n_{j,k}^{\text{C}}} p_{j,k}^q \quad (3)$$

where $n_{j,k}^{\text{C}}$ is the capacity of ATSU j during time window k . $p_{j,k}^q$ is the probability that the demand of ATSU j during time window k is q . Referring to our previous research [21], although directly computing Equation 3 requires complex joint probability-based combinatorial operations, since this study adopts sequential decision-making, we can transform these combinatorial operations into iterative computations:

$$p_{j,k}^{\text{NH}} \leftarrow p_{j,k}^{\text{NH}} - p_{j,k}^{n_{j,k}^{\text{MD}}} p_{i,j,k} \quad (4)$$

where $n_{j,k}^{\text{MD}}$ represents the maximum number of flights that may occupy time window k of ATSU j .

To more flexibly and efficiently utilise airspace resources, an overload tolerance $\zeta^0 \in [0, 1)$ for a time window of an ATSU is defined. Specifically, it ensures the probability that the demand within the ATSU is less than or equal to ζ^0 . Therefore, the DCB constraint can be expressed as:

$$1 - p_{j,k}^{\text{NH}} \leq \zeta^0 \quad (5)$$

We use $r_{j,k}^{\text{RM}}$ to represent the remaining maximum occupancy rate of ATSU j during time window k by the currently added flight, subject to satisfying the DCB constraint. It can be expressed as:

$$r_{j,k}^{\text{RM}} = \begin{cases} \frac{p_{j,k}^{\text{NH}} + \zeta^0 - 1}{n_{j,k}^{\text{C}} p_{j,k}^{\text{C}}} & n_{j,k}^{\text{MD}} \geq n_{j,k}^{\text{C}} \\ 1 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (6)$$

Ultimately, it can be conveniently determined whether the newly added flight i satisfies the DCB constraint by the following discriminative condition:

$$p_{i,j,k} \leq r_{j,k}^{\text{RM}} \quad (7)$$

B. Adaptive directed spatio-temporal graph generation

This study generates a directed spatio-temporal graph based on flight and DCB requirements for optimal path searching. ‘Adaptive’ means that a unique spatio-temporal graph is generated for each flight.

1) *Edge generation constraints:* In this study, waypoints on the ATSU boundaries (i.e., entry and exit points) and their connections within the ATSU are used as vertexes and edges, respectively, to generate the planar graph G^{P} for the DCB scenario. Graph G^{P} 's vertexes are labelled as (x, y) , which represent the waypoint's position coordinates. Then, a spatio-temporal graph for each non-hotspot-free flight will be generated, denoted by G_i for flight i . Graph G_i 's vertexes are labelled as (x, y, t) , where the first two parameters represent the waypoint's position coordinates and the last one represents flight i 's CTA to the waypoint. The edge generation of Graph G_i 's satisfies the following constraints:

- DCB constraint:** The flight must not cause the overload probability of the ATSU to exceed the tolerance.
- Speed constraint:** The flight speed must be within the performance range of the aircraft.
- Fuel consumption constraint:** The potential minimum fuel consumption of the flight must not exceed the preset maximum fuel consumption within the airspace of interest.
- ATSU continuity constraint:** Two connected edges must not lie within the same ATSU, in compliance with ATM operating rules (flights must be handed over to the next ATSU at waypoints on the ATSU boundary).
- Approaching constraint:** To improve the efficiency of graph generation, the tail (target) of a directed edge is always closer (straight-line distance) to the destination than its head (source).

For the sake of clarity, we use \mathbf{v}^{\oplus} to represent vertex \oplus and $\mathbf{v}^{\oplus} = (x_{i,j}^{\oplus}, y_{i,j}^{\oplus}, t_{i,j}^{\oplus})$, the former two parameters are position coordination and the third one is the corresponding CTA. \oplus can be S, T, O and D representing directed edge e 's source and target, flight i 's origin and destination of the airspace of interest, respectively. S, T, O and D are for Source, Target, Origin and Destination, respectively. Therefore, $t_{i,j}^{\text{T}} = t_{i,j}^{\text{S}} + \frac{d(\mathbf{w}^{\text{S}}, \mathbf{w}^{\text{T}})}{v_i}$, where \mathbf{w} represents a waypoint and $d(\mathbf{w}_1, \mathbf{w}_2)$ represents the planar straight-line distance between two waypoint. This paper typically uses \mathbf{w} to represent nodes when discussing

planar graphs and v to represent nodes when discussing spatio-temporal graphs.

Then, for flight i 's edge e in ATSU j at time window k to be generated, the DCB constraint can be represented as:

$$p_{i,j,k}(v^S) \leq r_{j,k}^{\text{RM}}, k \in K_{i,j}^{\text{S,T}} \quad (8)$$

where $p_{i,j,k}(v^S)$ represents the probability that flight i occupies ATSU j at time window k with v^S as source. $K_{i,j}^{\text{S,T}}$ represents the set of time windows during which flight i occupies ATSU j , with v^S and v^T as the source and target (including CTAs).

The fuel consumption constraint can be expressed as:

$$c_i^{\text{A,min}}(v^O, v^S) + c_i(v^S, v^T) + c_i^{\text{P,min}}(v^T, v^D) \leq c_i^{\text{max}} \quad (9)$$

where $c_i^{\text{A,min}}(v^O, v^S)$ represents flight i 's minimum achievable fuel consumption from v^O to v^S on current graph G_i (achievable: considering all constraints), $c_i(v^S, v^T)$ represents flight i 's fuel consumption from v^S to v^T , $c_i^{\text{P,min}}(v^T, v^D)$ represents flight i 's potential minimum fuel consumption from v^T to v^D on graph G^{P} (potential: considering no constraints), and c_i^{max} denotes flight i 's preset maximum fuel consumption in the airspace of interest. Since e in this paper represents a segment of constant-speed motion of the aircraft, and according to BADA, the economic speed of each aircraft type (i.e., the speed that achieves the lowest fuel consumption per unit distance) can be known, potential minimum fuel consumption $c_i^{\text{P,min}}(v^T, v^D)$ can be expressed as:

$$c_i^{\text{P,min}}(v^T, v^D) = d_{G^{\text{P}}}^{\text{min}}(w^T, w^D) \times u_i(v_i^{\text{E}}) \quad (10)$$

where $d_{G^{\text{P}}}^{\text{min}}(w^T, w^D)$ represents the distance of shortest path from v^T to v^D on graph G^{P} , $u_i(v)$ represents the fuel consumption per unit distance of flight i at speed v , and v_i^{E} denotes flight i 's economic speed. $d_{G^{\text{P}}}^{\text{min}}(w, w')$ can be obtained using a general shortest path algorithm (e.g., Dijkstra [22]).

The speed constraint can be expressed as:

$$v_{i,j,k}^{\text{min}} \leq v_e \leq v_{i,j,k}^{\text{max}} \quad (11)$$

where v_e denotes the speed represented by edge e , and $v_{i,j,k}^{\text{min}}$ and $v_{i,j,k}^{\text{max}}$ are flight i 's minimum and maximum speeds, respectively, in ATSU j at time window k , which can be preset according to, such as aircraft performance, airlines preference, ATC requirement and airspace situation in practice.

The ATSU continuity constraint can be expressed as:

$$\text{sub}(e^{\text{S,T}}) \subseteq \{e^{\text{S',T'}} \mid \text{S}' = \text{T}, \text{T}' \notin j_{e^{\text{S,T}}}\} \quad (12)$$

where $e^{\text{S,T}}$ represents the edge with v^S and v^T respectively as the source and target, $\text{sub}(e^{\text{S,T}})$ represents the set of the subsequent edges after $e^{\text{S,T}}$, and $j_{e^{\text{S,T}}}$ represents the ATSU where $e^{\text{S,T}}$ is located.

The Approaching constraint can be expressed as:

$$d(w^T, w^D) < d(w^S, w^D) \quad (13)$$

which means that the flight approaches the destination.

Figure 5. Implementation of hybrid ATFM measures through graph generation: an example. For the origin o and destination d , their subscripts (numbers) are used to distinguish the different times they represent. For the waypoint v_n , their superscripts (primes) are used to differentiate the times they represent, while their positions are the same. In the spatio-temporal graph, hotspot ATSUs are represented by three-dimensional shapes, where the cross-section represents the spatial extent of the area, and the height represents the time range during which it is active.

2) *Hybrid ATFM measure realisation by graph*: The proposed method uses hybrid ATFM measures, including rerouting, speed control, ground delay, and their combination, by specific generation approaches (Figure 5 for an example).

The **ground delay** strategy is implemented by generating several origins with the same location (where the flight enters the airspace of interest) and the different times. If we assume that the flight trajectory from the departure airport to its entry point in the airspace of interest remains unchanged, then these origins can represent different departure times, thereby implementing ground delay. To balance computational load and optimisation, when generating a G_i , the ground delay time is set within a time range T^{G} , and discrete values are taken at intervals of ΔT^{O} within this range to generate starting points representing different departure times. Thus, the set of origins $o \in O_i$ can be expressed as:

$$O_i = \left\{ (x_i^{\text{O}}, y_i^{\text{O}}, t) \mid \begin{array}{l} t = t_i^{\text{O}} + n \times \Delta T^{\text{O}}, \\ n \times \Delta T^{\text{O}} \leq T^{\text{G}}, n \in N \end{array} \right\} \quad (14)$$

where n denotes the set of natural numbers.

The **rerouting** strategy is implemented by connecting two neighbouring nodes as an edge based on the aforementioned constraints to represent different paths. For example, in the graph of the given example, v_2 can choose to connect with v_4 or v_5 to form an edge in order to bypass the hotspot ATSU blocking its path.

The **speed control** strategy is implemented by connecting targets that represent the same location but different times from

a source, generating multiple edges to represent different flight speeds. This study uses flight i 's economic speed as a baseline, with ΔV as the interval, to discretely sample alternative speeds within the speed range $[v_{i,j,k}^{\min}, v_{i,j,k}^{\max}]$, and then generates edges based on the constraints. When generating a directed edge representing the flight i 's trajectory from $\mathbf{V}_a = (x_a, y_a, t_a)$ to waypoint $\mathbf{w}_b = (x_b, y_b)$, the set of candidate nodes for waypoint \mathbf{w}_b with different speeds (i.e., $\mathbf{v} \in \mathbf{V}_{b(\leftarrow a)}$) can be expressed as:

$$\mathbf{V}_{b(\leftarrow a)} = \left\{ (x_b, y_b, t) \left| \begin{array}{l} t = t_a + \frac{d(\mathbf{w}_a, \mathbf{w}_b)}{v_i}, \\ v_i = v_i^E + n \times \Delta V, \\ n \in \mathbb{Z}, v_i \in [v_{i,j,k}^{\min}, v_{i,j,k}^{\max}] \end{array} \right. \right\} \quad (15)$$

where v_i^E denotes flight i 's economic speed and \mathbb{Z} denotes the set of integers.

C. Incremental path-search with admissible heuristic function

To meet the computational speed requirements of the tactical phase, this study developed an incremental path-searching approach to significantly reduce computation time. An admissible heuristic function was designed for the algorithm to ensure optimal trajectory generation. A heuristic function is said to be admissible if it never overestimates the cost of reaching the goal, i.e. the cost it estimates to achieve the goal is not higher than the lowest possible cost from the current point in the path [23].

In the proposed admissible heuristic function, the evaluation function consists of actual cost and estimated cost:

$$f_{G_i}^E(\mathbf{v}) = f_{G_i}^A(\mathbf{v}) + f_{G_i}^H(\mathbf{v}) \quad (16)$$

where $f_{G_i}^E(\mathbf{v})$, $f_{G_i}^A(\mathbf{v})$ and $f_{G_i}^H(\mathbf{v})$ are the evaluation function of vertex \mathbf{v} , actual cost from the origin to vertex \mathbf{v} , and estimated cost from vertex \mathbf{v} to the destination in weighted directed graph G_i , respectively.

The actual cost is the sum of the weights of the path with the minimum total weight from the starting point (virtual origin) to the current vertex, i.e., $f_{G_i}^A(\mathbf{v}) = c_i^{A,\min}(\mathbf{v}^O, \mathbf{v})$. Since the cost from the current vertex to the virtual destination includes both fuel consumption and delay time, this paper defines the estimated cost by separately taking the potential minimum values of these two parts, denoted by $c_{G_i}^{P,\min}(\mathbf{v})$ and $d_{G_i}^{P,\min}(\mathbf{v})$ respectively. Thus, $f_{G_i}^H(\mathbf{v})$ is expressed as:

$$f_{G_i}^H(\mathbf{v}) = c_{G_i}^{P,\min}(\mathbf{v}) + \alpha \times d_{G_i}^{P,\min}(\mathbf{v}) \quad (17)$$

where α is a weighting coefficient used to adjust the balance between fuel consumption costs and delay costs. Given that

commercial aviation users value punctuality more, this study prioritises minimising delay time first and fuel consumption second. Therefore, α can be set to a significantly large value in this context.

When calculating $c_{G_i}^{P,\min}(\mathbf{v})$ and $d_{G_i}^{P,\min}(\mathbf{v})$, it needs to be assumed that the flight proceeds along the shortest path from the current vertex to the destination on graph G^P (i.e., flight distance is $d_{G^P}^{\min}(\mathbf{w}_v, \mathbf{w}^D)$, where \mathbf{w}_v denotes the waypoint corresponding to the current vertex \mathbf{v}). Based on the shortest path distance, the speed $v_i^{\text{ND}}(\mathbf{v})$ that will just avoid delay is first calculated as:

$$v_i^{\text{ND}}(\mathbf{v}) = \frac{d_{G^P}^{\min}(\mathbf{w}_v, \mathbf{w}^D)}{t_i^{\text{PD}} - t_i^v} \quad (18)$$

The calculation can then be divided into the following cases:

- i. If the speed $v_i^{\text{ND}}(\mathbf{v})$ does not exceed the economic speed v_i^E , $c_{G_i}^{P,\min}(\mathbf{v})$ is calculated as the fuel consumption at economic speed v_i^E , and $d_{G_i}^{P,\min}(\mathbf{v})$ equals 0;
- ii. If the speed $v_i^{\text{ND}}(\mathbf{v})$ is greater than the economic speed v_i^E but does not exceed flight i 's maximum speed v_i^{\max} , $c_{G_i}^{P,\min}(\mathbf{v})$ is calculated as the smaller value between the fuel consumption at speed $v_i^{\text{ND}}(\mathbf{v})$ and the remaining fuel at vertex \mathbf{v} , and $d_{G_i}^{P,\min}(\mathbf{v})$ is calculated as the delay time at speed $v_i^{\text{ND}}(\mathbf{v})$, i.e., equals 0;
- iii. If the speed $v_i^{\text{ND}}(\mathbf{v})$ exceeds flight i 's maximum speed v_i^{\max} , $c_{G_i}^{P,\min}(\mathbf{v})$ is calculated as the smaller value between the fuel consumption at the maximum speed v_i^{\max} and the remaining fuel at vertex \mathbf{v} , and $d_{G_i}^{P,\min}(\mathbf{v})$ is calculated as the delay time at the maximum speed v_i^{\max} .

In case i, the calculation of $c_{G_i}^{P,\min}(\mathbf{v})$ does not need to consider the remaining fuel. For the calculation of $d_{G_i}^{P,\min}(\mathbf{v})$, when the remaining fuel is insufficient to support the desired speed (i.e., $v_i^{\text{ND}}(\mathbf{v})$ in case ii, v_i^{\max} in case iii), using the maximum speed supported by the remaining fuel to calculate the delay time is closer to the actual value. However, this calculation requires solving a cubic equation (refer to BADA [24]), which is relatively time-consuming. Considering that the delay cost calculated using the desired speed is not greater than that calculated using the maximum speed supported by the remaining fuel, which satisfies the requirements of an admissible heuristic function, this paper uses the delay cost calculated with the desired speed.

Based on the above discussion, $c_{G_i}^{P,\min}(\mathbf{v})$ and $d_{G_i}^{P,\min}(\mathbf{v})$ can, respectively, be expressed as Equation 19 and Equation 20, where $c_i^R \mathbf{v}$ denotes flight i 's remaining fuel at vertex \mathbf{v} , which is equal to $c_i^{\max} - c_i^{A,\min}(\mathbf{v}^O, \mathbf{v})$.

$$c_{G_i}^{P,\min}(\mathbf{v}) = \begin{cases} d_{G^P}^{\min}(\mathbf{w}_v, \mathbf{w}^D) \times u_i(v_i^E) & v_i^{\text{ND}}(\mathbf{v}) \leq v_i^E \\ \min\{d_{G^P}^{\min}(\mathbf{w}_v, \mathbf{w}^D) \times u_i(v_i^{\text{ND}}(\mathbf{v})), c_i^R \mathbf{v}\} & v_i^E < v_i^{\text{ND}}(\mathbf{v}) \leq v_i^{\max} \\ \min\{d_{G^P}^{\min}(\mathbf{w}_v, \mathbf{w}^D) \times u_i(v_i^{\max}), c_i^R \mathbf{v}\} & v_i^{\text{ND}}(\mathbf{v}) > v_i^{\max} \end{cases} \quad (19)$$

$$d_{G_i}^{P,\min}(\mathbf{v}) = \begin{cases} 0 & v_i^{\text{ND}}(\mathbf{v}) \leq v_i^{\max} \\ \left(\frac{d_{G^P}^{\min}(\mathbf{w}_v, \mathbf{w}^D)}{v_i^{\max}} + t_i^v - t_i^{\text{PD}}\right) & v_i^{\text{ND}}(\mathbf{v}) > v_i^{\max} \end{cases} \quad (20)$$

IV. SIMULATION EXPERIMENTS

The experimental environment for this study is Python 3.11, running on macOS with an Apple M1 Pro chip and 16GB of memory. The simulation data for this experiment is based on historical real flight plan data from Europe, covering the period from December 16 to 22, 2019, in the Data Demand Repository 2 (DDR2) format.

A. Scenario and parameter setup

This study's simulation experiments use the HYPER-SOLVER project's validation scenarios, as shown in Figure 6. Since the 9 ATSU in this scenario are newly constructed by the project meaning they have no nominal capacities, the historical operational peak is assumed to be the nominal capacity of the corresponding ATSU. As approximately half of the airspace in this scenario is free route airspace, the waypoints on the ATSU boundaries were obtained through clustering of historical data. Based on the obtained waypoints, a graph is constructed.

Aircraft operations follow the actual distribution, utilising the eight most common aircraft types (A320, B737, A330, B777, A350, B787, A380, and B767), with flight performance modelled using BADA. Flight plans were generated according to the spatio-temporal distribution in historical data, by randomly assigning aircraft types, waypoints, and corresponding entry times. The corresponding times at other waypoints were calculated based on the typical cruising speeds of the assigned aircraft type. To simplify the scenario, this experiment does not consider altitude changes, and flight performance parameters at FL350 are used. To conduct pressure testing, 7 traffic density scenarios were established, with 5000, 5500, 6000, 6500, 7000, 7500, and 8000 flights per 24 hours, respectively. In a scenario with 5000 flights, there are typically dozens of hotspots, while in a scenario with 8000 flights, hotspots become prevalent, with the demand in some ATSUs approaching nearly twice their capacity. Each traffic density scenario is randomly generated for 10 instances, resulting in a total of 70 instances.

Flight uncertainty is instantiated as a normal distribution. Based on prior related studies [25], the arrival time error at each waypoint grows linearly at a rate of 0.25 nautical miles per minute (denoted as e). Therefore, when computing a specific flight segment, the standard deviation $\sigma(t_{i, \overrightarrow{p_{i,n-1} p_{i,n}}})$ is assigned a value of $\frac{e \times t_{i, \overrightarrow{p_{i,n-1} p_{i,n}}}}{1.96 \times \sigma_{i, \overrightarrow{p_{i,n-1} p_{i,n}}}}$, which means there is a 95% probability that the error falls within e . Overload tolerance ζ^0 is set as 5%. Flight i 's preset maximum fuel consumption c_i^{\max} is an additional 10% above the fuel consumption of its initial flight plan.

B. Comparative models

To verify the key features of the proposed method, four sub-models are constructed using an ablation approach for the ATFM measure. These models are named GRS (the proposed method), GR, GS, and G, where G, R, and S represent ground delay, rerouting, and speed control, respectively. The model

Figure 6. Airspace in the simulation experiment scenario, where each ATSU is composed of several real sectors, equivalent to a larger 'sector' to match the enhanced conflict management capabilities of the ATC solver in the HYPER-SOLVER project.

TABLE I. FEATURES OF COMPARATIVE MODELS

Model	Feature			
	Ground delay	Rerouting	Speed control	Uncertainty
GRS	✓	✓	✓	✓
GR	✓	✓	-	✓
GS	✓	-	✓	✓
G	✓	-	-	✓
GRS-D	✓	✓	✓	-
CASA	✓	-	-	-
ILP	✓	-	-	-

names indicate the specific ATFM measure implemented in each model. D represents determinism, where the uncertainty model is removed. Besides, a practical CASA based on FCFS heuristic is used for practicality comparison, and an Integer Linear Programming (ILP) [12] is employed to evaluate mathematical boundaries. It should be noted that, due to technical limitations, both CASA and ILP are only compatible with ground delay. The features of these models are shown in Table I.

C. Performance test

Since all models in the experiment can utilise ground delay, the proposed method theoretically ensures the elimination of all hotspots. Therefore, this experiment primarily focuses on analysing and discussing the performance of the proposed method in terms of efficiency (delay and fuel consumption), computation time, and the usage of ATFM measures.

1) *Efficiency*: Figure 7 illustrates the efficiency metrics (delay and additional fuel consumption) from the performance evaluation. For delay time (sub-figures a, b, and c), both

the number of delayed flights and the delay time increase with traffic density. Since this study prioritises minimising delay time as the primary optimisation objective, model GRS, with its comprehensive ATFM measures, generally achieves shorter delays compared to other models in most scenarios. Interestingly, in the scenario with 8000 flights, the delay time of model GRS exceeds that of model GS. This may be because, under extremely high traffic density, rerouting increases flight distance and flight time, further depleting the already scarce airspace resources, triggering more severe congestion and exacerbating delays. Subsequent flights then face additional delays to alleviate the congestion. In terms of additional fuel consumption (sub-figures d and e), since ground delay does not increase fuel consumption, the additional fuel consumption of model G is consistently zero across all scenarios. The additional fuel consumption induced by speed control is significantly lower than that caused by rerouting. The additional fuel consumption of model GRS is very similar to that of model GR, except in the scenario with 8000 flights, where model GRS shows higher additional fuel consumption. This could be because model GRS, with the added option of speed control compared to model GR, provides more feasible solutions in high-density scenarios by combining rerouting and speed control to avoid longer delays. In a scenario with 6000 flights, which closely resembles real-world traffic density, the proposed method (model GRS) demonstrates the following average metrics across all experimental scenarios: the number

of delayed flights is 466.9, the average delay time for all flights is 0.77 minutes per flight, the average delay time for delayed flights is 9.85 minutes per flight, the average additional fuel consumption is 1.52 kilograms per flight, and the rate of additional fuel consumption is 0.03%. It should be noted that, although we have made every effort to ensure the experimental scenario is as close to reality as possible, these parameters are still for reference only and do not represent actual operational conditions. This is primarily due to the current inability to determine the actual capacities of ATSU.

2) *Computing time*: Figure 8 presents the statistical data of computation time across all experimental scenarios. It can be observed that Model GRS, which employs a greater number of ATFM measures, results in larger spatio-temporal graphs and, consequently, longer computation times. This is particularly evident in high-density scenarios, where an increase in conflicts leads to a higher frequency of graph construction, greater difficulty in resolving overloads (often due to a smaller feasible solution space), and larger spatio-temporal graph scales, all of which are time-consuming. Nevertheless, even under the highest traffic density in the experiments—8000 flights in one day—the total computation time is only approximately 800 seconds, with an average computation time of just 0.10 seconds per flight. Considering the HYPERSOLVER project’s envisioned application of a regulated block duration of 2 hours, the computation time for each regulated block in this study varies based on specific scenarios and is primarily influenced

Figure 7. Efficiency index (delay and additional fuel consumption), with the coloured shading in the figure representing the standard deviation of the corresponding data.

(a) Total computing time

(b) Average computing time

Figure 8. Computing time, including both model construction and optimisation solving time, with the coloured shading in the figure representing the standard deviation of the corresponding data.

by traffic density, but it rarely exceeds 200 seconds. Therefore, the proposed method demonstrates the potential to meet the requirements of tactical DCB.

3) *Usage of ATFM measures*: Figure 9 illustrates the average number of ATFM measures (ground delay, rerouting, speed control) employed by each model across all test cases. It can be observed that the preference for using ATFM measures, from highest to lowest, is ground delay, speed control, and rerouting. One primary reason for this may be that when traffic density exceeds a certain threshold, many flights are forced to adopt ground delay to eliminate hotspots, regardless of whether speed control or rerouting is also employed. Regarding rerouting, if a small-scale manoeuvre is sufficient to eliminate the hotspot, there may be an equivalent speed control solution with lower additional fuel consumption. On the other hand, if a large-scale manoeuvre is required to eliminate the hotspot, this would likely result in significantly longer flight times; in such cases, there is probably an equivalent ground delay solution, which avoids additional fuel consumption altogether. Even so, we must still emphasise the important role of rerouting in expanding the solution space and enhancing optimisation. It is worth emphasising that the size of the ATSU s constructed in the validation scenarios of the HYPERSOLVER project is several times larger than a typical sector, which may have somewhat limited the effectiveness of rerouting.

Figure 9. Usage of ATFM measures, where each measure is counted once if a regulated flight plan utilises all three types of ATFM measures simultaneously.

D. Baseline comparison

The proposed method is compared with the CASA and ILP methods under the sliding block-solving framework introduced by the HYPERSOLVER project (refer to Figure 2). Table II shows the average performance metrics in a scenario with 6500 flights.

TABLE II. COMPARATIVE RESULTS IN 6500-FLIGHT SCENARIOS

	GRS-D	CASA	ILP
Number of delayed flights	1046.6	5070.0	1121.3
Average delay time for all flights (min/flight)	2.07	26.15	2.15
Average delay time for delayed flights (min/flight)	12.84	33.53	12.45
Average computation time (s/flight)	5.06×10^{-3}	7.62×10^{-5}	1.45×10^{-1}

For the metrics of the number of delayed flights and the average delay time for all flights, the proposed method achieves reductions of 79.4% and 92.1%, respectively, compared to CASA. Interestingly, the proposed method even outperforms the ILP method in these two metrics. This is because, on the one hand, the sliding block-solving framework limits the global optimality advantages of ILP. On the other hand, the proposed method further enhances optimality by leveraging rerouting and speed control. While the improvement over ILP in terms of optimality is not groundbreaking, it is important to emphasise that the proposed method is transparent and can efficiently accommodate uncertainty models and custom optimisation models for individual flights, which is significant for enhancing its application potential. Additionally, in large-scale scenarios or scenarios with a smaller solution space, ILP may fail to find an optimal solution within the time constraints.

V. CONCLUSION

This study, conducted in a simulation environment based on European historical data, demonstrates that the proposed method can efficiently and rapidly solve large-scale tactical DCB problems. Combined with its theoretical properties, the study shows that the method meets the HYPERSOLVER project's technical development objectives: dynamic environment, high-speed computation, fairness and transparency, and high customisability.

The key findings of the study are as follows:

- 1) In the proposed method, rerouting does not always have a positive effect on delay-related metrics. When traffic density exceeds a certain threshold, the use of rerouting may have negative impacts. In such cases, a combination of ground delay and speed control, due to its smaller disruption to the airspace, may yield the best results.
- 2) When traffic density reaches a certain threshold, the computation time of the proposed method increases significantly. However, even so, within the sliding block-solving framework envisioned in this study, the method can still solve problems comfortably within the time requirements of tactical DCB.
- 3) The usage rates of ATFM measures in the proposed method, from highest to lowest, are ground delay, speed control, and rerouting.
- 4) The proposed method significantly outperforms the current practice method, CASA, in terms of optimisation. With the combined use of multiple ATFM measures, it even surpasses the mathematical boundary performance of using ground delay alone.

In summary, the proposed method shows promising application potential. However, to further validate and enhance its applicability, future research will incorporate more realistic environmental elements, such as more accurate uncertainty models, sector opening schemes, and flight altitude changes.

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